

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CROSS-PLY FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH CRACKS UNDER BIAXIAL LOADING CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

Composite structures are normally subjected to complex loading during operating processes that can generate multi-axial stress states at their surfaces. By using data from conventional uniaxial test of composite materials in the design processes, safety factors might be overestimated which lead to unnecessary enlargement of structure sizes. Compared to uniaxial testing method, biaxial testing approach provides more realistic data on the behaviours of composite structure under complex loading situations. Due to the lack of biaxial experimental data results of damaged fibre-reinforced composite laminates with geometrical discontinuities such as cracks or notches, this study is to investigate the effects of biaxial stress states on failure behaviours of composite laminates with cracks under static conditions. The cruciform type specimens with pre-crack in different sizes and orientation were tested under different in-plane biaxial loading ratio. Material system used in this study was glass fiber-reinforced epoxy with layup [0/90]_s. The crack initiation stresses are drawn on failure envelopes. Digital image correlation (DIC) technique was employed to generate strain field around the cracks during all tests. Full three-dimensional extended finite element method (XFEM) models with surface based cohesive behaviour approach or virtual crack closure technique were implemented by employing commercial ABAQUS code to simulate the initiation and propagation of the discrete cracks under biaxial loading conditions. The result showed that material attained higher load bearing capability under tensile-tensile conditions. The findings is useful in the design of composite structures with lower safety factor which decreases the weight of the composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Glass/carbon FRP composite materials have been increasingly applied to wind power industry to fabricate lightweight and stiff constructions. By using data from conventional uniaxial test of composite materials in the design processes, safety factors might be overestimated which might lead to unnecessary enlargement of structure sizes. Compared to uniaxial testing method, biaxial testing approach provides more realistic data on the behaviours of composite structure under complex loading situations. Due to the lack of biaxial experimental data results of damaged FRP composite materials with imperfections such as cracks or notches, the effects of biaxial stress states on failure behaviours of these composite laminates under static and dynamic conditions are investigated in this study.

Recently, various applications of biaxial testing using composite cruciform are presented in many aspects of engineering such as generating failure biaxial data, identifying the material characterization etc. Welsh et al. [1, 2] studied the ultimate biaxial strength of carbon/epoxy cross-fly and quasi-

isotropic laminates to generate the biaxial failure envelopes experimentally and analytically. Lecompte and Smits et al. [3, 4] proposed an inverse method to identify the composite material engineering constant by using DIC method to record the full field strain distribution on cruciform specimens under biaxial tension. Then these data were analyzed to calculate the material engineering constants which would be directly applied in the prediction of laminate behavior using FEM in the subsequent studies.

Biaxial testing methods using cruciform specimen on composite materials have improved due to the development of biaxial testing facilities, process monitoring methods and numerical tools. However, the biaxial data from these methods are limited because of the expensive costs of the testing equipment, sample preparation and experiment operation. Therefore, this paper focuses on investigating the failure behavior of composite laminates under biaxial stress states using an innovative testing system which is compatible with conventional uniaxial testing machine.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Material system

In this study, glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) unidirectional (UD) G17500 prepreg with a 0.15mm nominal ply thickness provided by Weihai Guangwei Composites was selected as material for all experiments. Table 1 presents the material properties.

Engineering constant		Value
<i>Longitudinal modulus</i> E_{11}	[GPa]	46
<i>Transverse modulus</i> $E_{22} = E_{33}$	[GPa]	13
<i>Poisson's Coefficient</i> ν_{12}	–	0.26
<i>Shear modulus</i> $G_{12} = G_{13}$	[GPa]	7
<i>Shear modulus</i> G_{23}	[GPa]	4.48

Table 1: Material elastic properties of G1750 unidirectional lamina [5].

Fracture properties of the cross-ply $[0/90]_{ns}$ laminate have been investigating using the Arcan testing method [6]. The fracture values are showed in the Table 2.

Fracture properties		Value
<i>Mode I fracture toughness</i> K_I	[MPa.m ^{1/2}]	46
<i>Mode II fracture toughness</i> K_{II}	[MPa.m ^{1/2}]	13
<i>Mode I energy release rate</i> G_{IC}	[MPa.m]	29.64
<i>Mode II energy release rate</i> G_{IIC}	[MPa.m]	3.47

Table 2: Material fracture properties of G1750 cross-ply lamina.

2.2 Specimen and layup configuration

Cruciform specimens with the dimensions and orientation showed in Figure 1 have been used. The specimen shape was designed to obtain a uniform far-field stress in central zone of the neat specimen by using FEM simulation [7].

All layups were manufactured by using hand layup. The composite panels were stacked together at the right sequence of $[0/90]_s$ with size of 320 mm by 200 mm. To prevent edge effect during the testing process, eight composite tabs including four tabs of 100 mm x 80mm and four tabs of 100 mm x 30 mm were prepared to obtain a symmetric pattern $[0/90]_{2s}$ by using the stacking process. Then these tabs were attached onto the sample at the four arms. After the stacking process, the samples was cured according to manufacturer instructions. Water jet cutting machine was used to cut the composite panel to the final geometry of samples (Figure 1). Finally, the crack was machined by milling machine with 1mm-diameter carbide tools.

Figure 1: Cruciform specimen dimensions and orientation. All dimensions are in mm.

2.3 Experimental procedure

All specimens were tested using the Instron 8502 universal testing machine with add-on fixture. This fixture has extended the capability of the uniaxial testing system to biaxial testing system with load carrying capacity in axial axis up to 250 kN and transverse axis up to 10 kN (figure 2). Each specimen was loaded under a constant displacement rate of 1 mm/min. The ratio between the axial force and transverse force was controlled by the Instron controller with Bluehill software. The value of critical loads were recorded when the crack started to propagate.

The biaxial tests were conducted using the samples with through-thickness centre cracks of 40 mm and 45 mm length with orientations of 0° and 45° . Transverse to axial stress ratios were 0:1, 0.333:1, 0.667:1, 0.8883:1, 1:1, 1:0.883, 1:0.667, 1:0.333 and 1:0. For the 45° crack specimens, only half of tests were done because of the symmetrical shape of the specimen.

A digital single-lens reflex camera was used to capture images of testing specimens every second. The specimen surfaces were sprayed by black paint to create speckle patterns. Images of testing processes were analyzed by VIC2D software and then generated the displacement fields.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the biaxial testing system.

3 DATA REDUCTION

3.1 Equivalent loaded area

The actual stress which is distributed over the cross-section of a testing sample is important to determine the behavior of a composite panel under biaxial loadings. However the cruciform geometry of specimens is non-uniform which can affect to the calculation of stress in axial and transverse directions. To bypass this problem, a method to calculate the equivalent area in the both directions was proposed. Tensile strength of the testing composite material is determined by uniaxial tensile testing according to ASTM standard D3039/3039M. The biaxial samples are then separately tested in uniaxial axial and transverse direction under tensile loading. Ultimate load when the sample failed was used to calculate the equivalent loaded area.

$$A_{eq} = P/\sigma_{ult} \quad (1)$$

Where A_{eq} is equivalent loaded area (mm^2), P is the ultimate load (N) and σ_{ult} is tensile strength (MPa).

After the equivalent loaded areas in both axial and transverse is determined. This values were used to calculate the stress in specimens during the biaxial tests.

3.2 Stress intensity factor

The stress intensity factor is important to evaluate the effects of a crack on laminate failure under biaxial loading. The mode I and mode II stress intensity factor values for a slanted crack under biaxial stress field can be express as [8]:

$$K_I = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a}(\cos^2\alpha + k\sin^2\alpha) \quad (2)$$

$$K_{II} = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a}(1 - k)\sin\alpha\cos\alpha \quad (3)$$

Where K_I and K_{II} are mode I and mode II stress intensity factors, σ is stress value, $2a$ is crack length, α is crack angle and k is biaxial load ratio.

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

For the FE modeling of the biaxial specimen, an eight-node brick element with reduced integration C3D8R available in ABAQUS is used. Mesh refinements are defined around the crack to archive a better result in simulation. The equivalent elastic properties of $[0/90]_s$ laminate are calculated using MATLAB and the properties were then assigned for the material properties of FE model. The FEM model of the biaxial specimen is showed in the Fig. 3 with the details of mesh around the crack notch. The crack growth is found without any branch crack in a self similar manner. The virtual crack closure technique were implemented to simulate the propagation of the discrete cracks under biaxial loading conditions.

Figure 3: FE domain with the mesh details, boundary conditions and loading conditions.

The energy-based damage evolution law based on a power law criterion is used for the damage propagation. The power law model is described by the following formula [9 dsaf]:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^m + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^n + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}}\right)^p \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

Where G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} are mode I, mode II and mode III energy release rates, m , n and p are empirical values which were determined from experiments. For the biaxial testing problems, the affect of mode III to the fracture behavior of laminated is neglected i.e. $p = 0$.

5 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

For the biaxial specimens tested, the crack grew from the notches and propagated to the tabs. The crack propagation paths are showed in the Fig. 4. Similar trend of crack propagation orientation was found with other specimens in varying load ratios and crack lengths. The first set of experiments were performed on the samples with crack orientation of 0° . The critical axial stress vs critical transverse stress graphs for 0° and 45° crack specimens were shown in the Fig. 5 and Fig. 6.

Figure 4: Crack propagation paths for (a) 0° crack and (b) 45° crack.

Figure 5: Plot of critical axial stress vs critical transverse stress for 0° crack sample with crack length of 40 mm and 45 mm [7].

Figure 6: Plot of critical axial stress vs critical transverse stress for 45° crack sample with crack length of 40 mm and 45 mm [7].

The data shown in Fig. 5 illustrated the effect of transverse stress to the ultimate failure stresses under biaxial loading. In the case of low transverse stress, the specimens could withstand a higher amount of axial tensile stress than the uniaxial test case i.e. 1:0 loading ratio. When the transverse stress became much higher than the axial stress i.e. the loading ratio from 0.667:1 to 0:1, the crack was observed to propagate without the destruction of the specimen immediately. The specimen was destroyed when the transverse stress reached the material tensile strength. This could be explained by the crack closure mechanism. The axial load tended to open up the crack and the transverse load tended to close it. If the transverse force became much higher than the axial force, the specimen failed when the stress reached the material strength called a notch-insensitive manner. Besides it was clear to see that stress values of the 40 mm crack case were higher than the 45 mm crack case. Therefore the crack length affected the ultimate failure values of the specimens. However if the ratio between the crack length and the width of gauge area in the specimen was low enough, this effect could be neglected. In the 45° crack case (Fig. 6), the transverse stress had the same effect to the ultimate failure stresses in stress ratio from 1:0 to 1:1 with the the 0° crack case. The ultimate failure stress values in the 45° crack case were also higher than the 0° crack case. The reason was that the crack opening mode I in the 45° crack case is lower than in the 0° crack case and this mode was dominant in fracture of composite laminate.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A method is presented for the investigation of the fracture behavior of composite cross-ply laminate under biaxial loading. Failure envelope was drawn to determine the effect of transverse stress/force to the ultimate fracture stress values of the specimens. The result showed that material attained higher load bearing capability under the present of transverse stress. The findings is useful in the design of composite structures with lower safety factor which decreases the weight of the composite structures. Scopes for future work are to measure the missing data in failure envelope and to conduct the full simulation for XFEM model of biaxial testing specimens.

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